

FACTORS THAT HELP IMPROVE SPEAKING SKILLS

Amanboyeva Ra'noxon

teacher of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10819324>

Abstract. *The article is devoted to look at the importance of speaking skills and how to develop them. Improving speaking skills can be useful in many social situations.*

Keywords. *Articulating, listening, acting, reading aloud, singing, expanding vocabulary.*

Everyone speaks to some extent or other. The ordinary individual may anticipate to say thousands of words every day. Some job contexts, however, need far more. If you enhance your speaking abilities, you will discover that a plethora of opportunities will suddenly present themselves.

Unfortunately, good speaking abilities are frequently viewed as something you either have or don't. As a result, many of us come to accept a specific level of speaking competence and stay there. However, it is feasible to improve your speaking abilities, and there are several ways you may use to do so.

Effective speaking entails combining a variety of talents to communicate and create an effect. To be understood, you must first locate the right words, arrange them correctly, then pronounce them correctly. Other important components are emphasis, cadence, and delivery. Consider a brilliant stand-up comedian: merely memorizing and repeating the words is insufficient to deliver an engaging performance and connect with an audience.

There are many ways that good communication can improve your life. It allows you to communicate, convince and entertain, just like a great artist.

If you want to have a better social life, it's likely that you'll need to talk. Having the ability to talk will help you engage in a variety of conversations and help you decide when to shut up and listen. Conversations are the foundation of most relationships and friendships, and having the ability to talk clearly doesn't necessarily mean you'll have better social relationships. But it can be a great starting point.

If you want to advance in your career, it's important to have good conversation skills. These skills can also be beneficial in meetings and presentations. If you're not good at talking, employers may not even consider hiring you unless they have a long, formal conversation with you. A job interview is more than just a way to observe how potential employees react under pressure. It is a test of your listening and communication skills. Great ideas aren't enough. You need to be good at conveying them.

You may wish to share your thoughts in settings other than the workplace. Consider a cause to which you would like to devote your time and efforts. Speaking abilities will assist you spread the word. This is true whether you're trying to raise awareness about the plight of the environment or raise funds to fix the roof of your local church or community center.

If you are devoted to furthering a certain set of beliefs or policies, you should make an effort to understand how to successfully convey them. Engaging people's interests is likely to provide greater outcomes than yelling slogans at them.

In order to improve speaking skills a student should accept some rules. The solution is generally progressive improvement accompanied by beneficial habits. Let's take a look at some of these behaviors.

Articulate words accurately

A few words in English are infamous for stumbling individuals up when it comes to articulation. Commonly misspoke words incorporate exaggeration, exemplification, coffee, viscount, and evil. You'll be able hazard shame in case you get these off-base, even if many individuals do so. This is often particularly vital in the event that you are articulating words inaccurately amid work interviews.

If you are not a native speaker of English, then there are some words – such as strengths – that will require a lot of practice. However, this will be worth it if you have a support group made up of other English language students.

Pronouncing the words you say will make you sound authoritative and avoid misunderstandings. Pronouncing the right words will make you sound confident, and it will also make your audience feel confident.

Listening to spoken English

The most important way we learn a language is by listening to spoken English. This is true both as an adult and as a child. And when it comes to listening to spoken English, we have never had it so easy. From podcasts and audiobooks to talk radio and TV, you can listen to hours of English a day and grow an ear for it.

You ought to stand by listening to the sort of material you might want to recreate. Assume you need to have useful conversations with partners. All things considered, paying attention to informed banter between informed individuals may be a valuable methodology. To be a smidgen more expressive, then, at that point, paying attention to improvisational parody, show, or verse may be the way to take.

Most importantly, attempt to pay attention to content that you view as locking in. In the event that you get exhausted and quit focusing, you're probably not going to get much from the activity

Read aloud

One exercise that is always worthwhile is to read something aloud. Many experienced writers recommend this as part of the editing process. If a sentence sounds good out loud, it's probably a good sentence. Reading aloud also offers several important benefits in everyday contexts. Canadian researchers have found that reading aloud makes it easier to remember what you read, which can be a great way to increase your vocabulary. Reading aloud also allows you to practice speaking skills and even solve problems. If you keep stumbling over certain phrases, you have nowhere to hide when reciting. Practice can also help with your pacing and speaking at a natural pace.

You don't have to read everything out loud. It can be considered a bit distracting if you do it on a crowded train. But the benefits are tangible, so devoting time to practicing reading aloud can be highly desirable.

Learn to sing

Learning to sing gives you a variety of skills that can be applied to everyday conversation and speech. You'll learn when and how to project your voice, become more aware of what's happening physiologically, and gain the confidence to perform in front of people.

Learn to act.

In addition, acting can help you face aspects of the language that you may not yet be familiar with. If you spend most of your time working on dry technical concepts, using creative language can be more than helpful.

Practice Poetry

Many of us have preconceived notions about poetry that can prevent us from truly enjoying and appreciating it. Unlike a novel or an essay, a poem is read aloud, just as lyrics are sung. Understanding the mechanics of a good poem will help you speak more fluently. The Creative Writing and Poetry Course at Newcastle University in Australia is a great place to learn about the art form. It takes six hours over three weeks.

Expand your vocabulary

The more words you know, the easier it will be for you to find the right word when you need it. A strong vocabulary isn't just about knowing as many words as possible, it's about being able to use them. We've all found ourselves understanding the sometimes elusive term. By increasing your vocabulary, you can ensure that you have the words you need to communicate effectively. You may think that a strong vocabulary is the result of extensive reading. The more words we consume, the more likely we are to assimilate. When many of us read, we can be tempted to skim over words we don't fully understand, or to infer their meaning based on the context. Some words may require some research to understand. Do you know the difference between "which" and "that"? What about "insurance" and "warranty"? In some cases, you may assume you know what certain words mean and accidentally put your foot in the middle. Misusing a word in a professional setting can be embarrassing, but it's not hard to check the meaning of a word online if you're not sure.

Talking to strangers

Talking effectively means that you consider the person you are talking to. If you're going to grow, you want to talk to as broad and diverse a group as possible. This means talking to strangers whenever you get the chance. It may happen that if you are open to them, there are often opportunities to chat with many different people.

Correcting Speech Disorders

A speech disorder or speech disorder is a condition that prevents you from speaking clearly. In some cases, they develop in childhood. For others, you may begin to suffer later in life. Speech disorders can vary. In some cases, they can be alleviated with exercise, education and psychological help. If you have more difficulty speaking in a certain emotional state, dealing with your emotions may be a necessary part of managing the disorder.

Practice Speaking

Standing and delivering a monologue in front of an informed audience is the ultimate test of your communication skills. If you can do that, you should be able to handle most speech problems.

For many, effective speaking skills are not always easy. For some, they require work, patience and determination. You can't expect to become a great speaker overnight. Developing fluency can take years or even decades of consistent work, regular practice, and reinforcing good habits. If that sounds scary, remember to focus on why you're doing it. Improving your speaking skills has many benefits both professionally and personally. Develop at your own pace and enjoy the sense of achievement that comes from expressing yourself well and participating in rewarding conversations.

REFERENCE

1. Liakin, D., Cardoso, W., & Liakina, N. (2017). [The pedagogical use of mobile speech synthesis \(TTS\): Focus on french liaison](#). *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 30(3-4), 348-365.
2. Liakin, D., Cardoso, W., & Liakina, N. (2015). [Learning L2 pronunciation with a mobile speech recognizer: French /y/](#). *CALICO Journal*, 32(1), 1-25.
3. Kaiser, D.J. (2017). IPronounce: Understanding pronunciation apps. Online Webinar, 8 June 2017. Recording and slides available at <http://ollren.org/events/past-events#s-lg-box-wrapper-17792711>
4. Kaiser, D. (2018). [Mobile-assisted pronunciation training: The iPhone pronunciation app project](#). *IATEFL Pronunciation Special Interest Group Journal*, (58), 38–52.
5. <https://www.futurelearn.com/info/blog/how-to-improve-speaking-skills>